

A model of self-knowledge for young athletes and a methodology for its implementation in the educational environment of sports organizations

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Abstract

The article examines the significance of personal self-awareness in contemporary society and its role in sports activity. In the context of global socio-cultural transformations, self-awareness is considered one of the key factors influencing important life decisions. Sports activity is viewed as an effective means for fostering self-awareness in young athletes, helping them to set life goals, develop a value system, and form an active life position. During the training process, young athletes become aware of their potential, seek to answer the question “Who am I?”, and gain opportunities for self-expression.

Drawing on the theoretical foundations of A. Maslow and K. Rogers, the study substantiates that the value–need sphere represents the main driving force in the development of self-awareness and personal growth. In this regard, the effective formation of these personal qualities within pedagogical and sports practice is identified as an urgent and relevant task.

Keywords: self-awareness, personal development, value system, sports activity, young athletes, life goals, self-expression, needs and motivation, pedagogical approach, personality formation.

Introduction

Until recently, the issue of personal self-awareness was not considered a central topic in the socio-cultural context. Greater attention was primarily given to professional self-awareness, particularly in relation to career choice. In many fields, the development of personal self-awareness remained formal and superficial. However, contemporary global transformations require individuals to adopt a more conscious and reflective attitude toward the processes occurring in their environment.

As a result, self-awareness is increasingly becoming one of the key factors in making important life decisions. It plays a crucial role in the formation of a value system, the development of personal identity, and the definition of long-term life goals.

Today, sports activity represents one of the most competitive and dynamic environments, significantly contributing to the develop-

ment of self-awareness in individuals.

This issue is especially relevant for young athletes. During the process of sports training, a child determines their life direction, sets goals, selects appropriate means and methods for achieving them, and gains opportunities for self-expression.

Sports activity fosters an active life position, supports the resolution of issues related to needs, values, and attitudes toward work, and creates a foundation for answering the question “Who am I?”. The deeper a child’s understanding of themselves, the higher their level of self-awareness and the greater their opportunities for achieving life goals.

According to A. Maslow and K. Rogers, the value–need sphere serves as the primary driving force that supports personal development and forms the mechanisms of self-awareness, self-development, and self-regulation. Consequently, pedagogical and sports practice face the important task of determining effective methods and tools for developing these personal qualities.

Research objective: To improve the methodology for the conscious selection of a type of sports activity through the development of self-awareness in students of a sports school.

Research objectives: To provide a theoretical substantiation of the effectiveness of a methodology for the conscious selection of a type of sports activity based on the formation of self-awareness in sports school students.

Result and discussion

To address the problem of designing a model of self-awareness in the process of selecting a type of sports activity for a young athlete, the modeling method was employed. Modeling is a specific method of scientific inquiry widely used in pedagogical research.

In pedagogical science, the modeling method has been substantiated in the works of V.G. Afanasyev, V.A. Venikov, B.A. Glinsky, I.B. Novik, V.A. Shtoff, and others. In our

Table. Model of self-awareness of a young athlete in the educational process of sports institutions

Purpose: formation of a person's readiness to consciously choose the type of sports activity.		
Tasks:		
1. 1. Study of scientific and educational-methodological literature covering the problems of self-awareness of the individual in choosing the type of sports activity and identification of theoretical and methodological approaches to the implementation of personality-oriented education in the self-awareness of young athletes.		
2. 2. Determine the set of pedagogical conditions aimed at forming a young athlete's readiness to choose the type of sports activity in sports institutions.		
3. 3. Enriching the young athlete's knowledge of "I-image" and "I-concept."		
4. 4. Developing the ability to apply information about oneself in practical activities.		
5. 5. Implementing a practical training program to develop preparedness for choosing a sport.		
Cognitive block	Motivational block	Activity-practical block
Knowledge of oneself, "I-image," individual characteristics and abilities, norms of behavior in situations of choice, the ability to use the information received about oneself, the ability to assess personal capabilities	Direction towards activating life self-determination, preserving the individual's self-esteem, choosing a type of activity based on needs, achieving success in the chosen activity, consciously performing actions, manifesting oneself in new social situations, and gaining social experience	Conscious selection of the type of sports activity based on the knowledge gained about oneself and individual characteristics, as well as the manifestation of personal qualities in the process of carrying out the chosen activity
Functions: cognition and analysis, diagnosis	Functions: propaedeutic, organizational, and practical-guiding.	Functions: cognitive, organizational, practical-orientational, control-evaluative, analytical
Methods: observation, conversation, persuasion, creating situations of choice and success, referring to social experience, setting an example, training, playing a game, demonstrating, conducting a survey and testing, analyzing the results of activities, self-assessment, self-analysis, self-control		
Forms: conversation, lectures (introductory, explanatory-demonstrative, problem-based, analytical), seminars, trainings, practical classes, consultations (group and individual), independent work, pedagogical practice.		
Resources: popular science and educational literature; working curricula, self-assessment questions, topics of independent work, bibliography; collections of situational problems and exercises, methodological instructions, library collection, scientific and educational journals, tables, visual aids (pictures, photographs), audiovisual aids (video recordings), lecture texts, notes for independent study, creative assignments, computers, screens, laptop, video camera, audio devices, equipment for movement and coordination exercises.		
Result: positive growth in readiness for conscious selection of the type of sports activity.		

view, one of the most comprehensive definitions was proposed by G.V. Sukhodolsky, who interprets modeling as the process of constructing a hierarchy of models that represent an existing system from different perspectives and through various tools. The central concept of this method is the model itself.

A model is an artificially created object presented in the form of diagrams, symbols, formulas, or material constructions that, in a simplified and generalized manner, reflect the properties, structure, and relationships between the elements of the original object.

Direct investigation of a real object is often associated with financial or technical difficulties; therefore, modeling serves as an effective alternative. According to V.G. Afanasyev, models can be conditionally divided into three

types:

Physical models, which possess properties similar to the original;

Material–mathematical models, whose physical nature differs from the prototype but allows for a mathematical description of its behavior;

Logical–semiotic models, which consist of signs, symbols, and structural schemes.

These types do not have rigid boundaries, and pedagogical models are mainly related to the second and third groups.

I.B. Novik defines modeling as an indirect theoretical or practical study of an object in which an auxiliary artificial or natural system, being in objective correspondence with the original, can replace it in certain relations and, as a result of its investigation, provide infor-

mation about the modeled object. The situations described in this definition represent the essential characteristics of modeling. Due to its broader and more comprehensive meaning, this definition was adopted as the main conceptual basis of the present study.

Thus, in applying the modeling method, we proceed from the general premise that all models share a common feature—the ability to reflect reality.

In designing the model of self-awareness of a young athlete, the following principles were taken into account: the interrelationship between theory and practice; the activity and conscious participation of the child in the educational process; professional orientation of the model; accessibility; time efficiency; and the use of the same educational material in different forms.

Through the application of the modeling method, a theoretical structural–functional model of a young athlete’s self-awareness was developed. In constructing this model and defining its content, we relied on the fundamental provisions of the psychological–cultural, sociological, and general psychological approaches to the self-determination of a young athlete within the educational environment of sports institutions. Therefore, the following section is devoted to substantiating the essence of each of these approaches and determining their role as a methodological basis for model development.

The psychological–cultural approach to the problem of self-awareness focuses on the individual’s striving for self-expression, which is formed through the internalization of historically developed forms and types of social activity (L.S. Vygotsky, N.B. Krylova, L.M. Karnozova, I.D. Frumin, V.D. Elkonin).

The general psychological approach is based on the individual’s awareness of their place in social relations and on the selection of a type of activity according to their abilities, capabilities, needs, interests, and motives.

According to Yu.K. Babansky, A.G. Kuznetsov, V.A. Slastenin, N.M. Yakovleva, and others, any pedagogical model can function successfully only under appropriate pedagogical conditions. E.V. Yakovlev distinguishes between necessary and sufficient conditions for the functioning of a model. Necessary conditions are those without which the model cannot operate effectively, whereas sufficient conditions ensure its normal and stable functioning.

Following this position, a set of pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the developed model has been identified. We adopt E.V. Yakovlev’s view that sufficient conditions are those that ensure the effective implementation of the model. The sufficiency of these conditions is confirmed by the positive results of the experimental work, particularly at its formative stage.

Thus, in our study, pedagogical conditions are understood as a set of necessary and sufficient measures that create the most favorable environment for the effective implementation of the model aimed at determining the developmental direction of a young athlete within the educational space of specialized sports institutions.

Accordingly, the effectiveness of these pedagogical conditions depends on:

- the creation of a productive educational environment in a sports institution;
- the establishment of supportive and guiding interactions between the teacher and the student;
- the implementation of pedagogical support methods that facilitate the conscious selection of a type of sports activity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study substantiates the necessity of a set of specific pedagogical conditions for the effective implementation of the model aimed at determining the developmental pathway of a young athlete in the process of selecting a type of sports activity within the educational environment of sports institutions. This conclusion is grounded in the principles of systems analysis. On this basis, a комплекс of pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the developed model was identified and described.

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Research interests

Theory and methodology of physical education; athlete development; gymnastics training; sports competition analysis; self-awareness in young athletes; pedagogical modeling in sports education.
